

IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI) ON HEALTHCARE JOBS AND TRAINING IN BAYELSA STATE, NIGERIA.

By

Blessing Oyinbrakemi Moroyei

Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State

Email: blessingmoroyei86@gmail.com, Phone: +2348060373888

&

Progress Oghenedikiyenke Samuel

Email: oghenedikiyenke@gmail.com, Phone: +2348132842073

ABSTRACT

The impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on healthcare delivery systems is perceived to be complex and a double edge sword with both potential benefits and obstacles capable of transforming the entire health sector. With this, healthcare workers are now faced with the task of upgrading themselves with AI-driven skills. This study examined the impact of AI on the healthcare jobs and trainings in Bayelsa state, Nigeria. Adopting the Socio-Technical System theory, the study provided a theoretical background, explaining how Ai-based training, skills as well curriculum is now part and parcel of healthcare sector. The STS theory provided a background to the rationale behind the relationship between health workers' productivity/efficiency and job displacements and the use of AI. Due to the nature of the population which comprises non-healthcare workers and healthcare workers the Yaro Yemeni's formula was used to determine the population sample of 400 respondents. However, the random and stratified sample technique was used for easy access of every character in the sampled population. Primary data were collected with the use of a structured questionnaire and were analyzed with use simple percentage, mean, standard deviation, tables, charts, and the Pearson product moment correlation with the aid of SPSS. Findings from the survey revealed that the application of AI in healthcare delivery services has drastically both a positive and negative impact on healthcare workers' productivity and efficiency. Conversely, the study confirmed that the use of AI has resulted to increase in job loss among healthcare workers. It is therefore recommended that all health organization in Nigeria, should design a clear organizational approach for AI integration with the aim of improving AI literacy and adaptability among both the healthcare workers and non-healthcare workers.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, AI-driven Skills, Healthcare, Worker's productivity.

INTRODUCTION

The world today is fast gravitating into the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in virtually all areas of production and services. Artificial intelligence has proven to be a game-changing

force in health sectors throughout the world offering prospects for significant development. In Africa, using AI in healthcare, especially in areas with limited resources, holds valuable promise in transforming and improving healthcare. As artificial intelligence continues to grow as afield and as a major player in our daily lives, it is also being met with backlash. Due to the unpredictable nature of the state of artificial intelligence advancement, as well as its ability to perform some tasks even better than humans, there is much uncertainty surrounding AI and its potential impact on jobs (Schmelzer, 2019). For example, many call centers were shut down during the Corona virus Pandemic as the main labour force shifted towards AI-focused applications that can handle large amounts of callers at a fraction of the cost for employers (Samuels, 2020).

Prior to the rise of AI in the globe the indices used for measuring productivity and efficiency of health workers in the health sector was different. Previously, from a macro perspective it was necessary that the health sector reforms need to address the performance of health workers, due to its labour-intensive nature (Franco et al., 2002). In general, the major impact of health sector reform on the workforce is in terms of changes in working conditions, payment, labour relations, the demand for certain skills, and terms of employment (Wiskow, 2006).

These changes threaten job security and often result in unrest among health care providers (Homedes & Ugalde, 2005). This is compounded by poor management at local level due to changes in roles and functions, unclear lines of authority and a lack of managerial skills and knowledge among managers (Dussault & Dubois, 2003; Kolehmainen-Aitkin, 2004). The lack of involvement by providers in planning and implementation causes a decline in the quality of care and increased absenteeism (Wiskow, 2006; Rigoli; Homedes & Ugalde, 2005; Kolehmainen-Aitken, 2004)

Statement of Problem

In reality the healthcare industry in Nigeria as it is with other developing countries is grappling with a myriad of pressing challenges that have put strain on its workforce. These difficulties span through various aspects of the healthcare system and create a complex and demanding environment for professionals in the field. As technology continues to advance, artificial intelligence (AI) is poised to play an increasingly significant role in shaping the future of the healthcare workforce. The impact of AI on healthcare is anticipated to be multidimensional and intricate, with both potential benefits and obstacles to navigating years ahead. AI-powered technologies hold promise for their ability to address some of the current issues faced by the healthcare workforce. By leveraging the capabilities of AI, there is an opportunity to boost efficiency and effectiveness across various healthcare processes and tasks (Reddy, 2024)

Interestingly, while European scholars and others in advanced societies have become acquainted with the occupational use of AI, very few studies have been conducted to address the impact of AI on healthcare jobs and training in Nigeria with particular reference to Bayelsa. However, there have been recent discoveries on the subject matter from scholars across the globe, for instance Rupa (2023) in his study considering the need for more integration of AI in the health sector as a significant paradigm shift there is a strong advocacy to look into the current challenges in the healthcare industry with the constant need to keep up with advancements in technology, medicine, and research. As such, Healthcare professionals in

Nigeria especially in rural areas must strive to remain current and knowledgeable about new treatment options, innovative technologies, and emerging diseases to provide the best care possible to their patients. Rupa concluded that the healthcare industry faces numerous challenges such as increasing costs, workforce shortages, and healthcare inequalities.

Addressing the impact of AI on health sector Esan (2023) postulated that the AI's impact on healthcare jobs is multifaceted, reconfiguring responsibilities and redefining the contours of various roles. This transformation is driven by the capacity of AI systems to process vast amounts of medical data, recognize patterns, and generate insights at speeds and accuracies that human capabilities alone cannot match. In effect, this augmentation of human capabilities rather than their replacement characterizes the evolving nature of healthcare jobs in an AI-infused landscape. Esan's (2023) viewed AI in the light of healthcare serves not as a disruptor but as a catalyst for evolution. The symbiotic relationship between AI and healthcare professionals exemplifies the synergy achievable when cutting-edge technology aligns with human expertise. Conclusively, Esan noted that as the journey of AI and healthcare continues, the industry stands poised to navigate challenges, and leverage opportunities, and pioneer a new era of medical excellence.

Ukeh and Anih (2024) in their study investigated the utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) tools for teaching and research purposes among students and lecturers at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State, discovered that lack of utilization of artificial intelligence-based tools for both teaching and research purposes among lecturers in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa which is suggestive to the fact there is a potential gap in the integration and adoption of such tools in the academic environment. Further efforts and initiatives may be needed to promote the effective implementation of artificial intelligence technologies to enhance teaching and research practices in these institutions. Meanwhile, the incorporation of AI tools in teaching and research represents a significant paradigm shift in higher education. Lecturers, embracing the potential of AI, are leveraging these tools to enhance the learning experience and streamline research processes.

Although Ukeh et al (2024) study which focused on the use of AI solving teaching and research problems is very contemporary, it doesn't address the impact of AI on health jobs or its impacts on healthcare workers' productivity and efficiency. In this current study, we shall attempt to expand our investigation by for investigating the impact of AI on health jobs and training by exploring the following areas which will cut-across the effect of AI-driven training on healthcare workers, the role of AI on the changes in tasks routine of healthcare workers. The adaptability of healthcare workers to the new shifts in skills due to the use of Ai, the use of AI contributes to the increased job displacement among healthcare providers and the contributions of AI based service patience well-being and satisfaction in Bayelsa state.

1.3 Research Problem

In line with the research problem, it is necessary to formulate research questions that would widen our scope of investigation in a specific direction. Thus, the research questions are designed to thematically overlap with the objectives of the study. In effect, the following research questions are posed accordingly:

Does AI play any significant role on health workers' productivity and efficiency in Bayelsa state?

Has the integration of AI contributed to the increased job displacement among healthcare providers in Bayelsa state?

1.4 Objectives of the study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of AI on Healthcare jobs and training in Bayelsa state. However, in order to explore on this overall objectives, this study shall be expanded by examining the following specific objectives in relation to the main objectives:

To examine the role of AI on health worker's productivity and efficiency in Bayelsa state.

To find out if the use of AI contributes to the increased job displacement among healthcare providers in Bayelsa state

1.5 Research Hypotheses

It is required that the hypotheses be stated in its alternate form. The research hypotheses will show the relationship between two or more variables. Statistically, it is a statement that predetermine that will affirm the predictability of the possible outcome of two or more variables in relation with each other. As such, the hypotheses for this study are:

There is a significant relationship between integration of AI and Healthcare workers' productivity/efficiency

There is a significant relationship between the application of AI in healthcare delivery and patients' satisfaction

Methods

This study was conducted healthcare workers and non-healthcare workers in Bayelsa state. It was a co-relational study which attempted to find out how the use of AI in healthcare delivery services have direct or indirect effect on healthcare jobs in Bayelsa state. As such, a self-structured questionnaire was used which was divided into 3 sections. In the 1st section of the questionnaire respondents filled in their general information – gender, occupation, education, age, and marital status. The 2nd section of the questionnaire referred to impact of AI-driven skills and tools in healthcare workers productivity and efficiency while the 3rd section contained questions regarding the impact of AI on the increased job loss among healthcare workers. With use of Yaro Yemeni's sample size determination, 400 respondents was sampled from the overall population which comprise non-healthcare workers and healthcare workers. The random and stratified sample technique was used for easy access of every character in the sampled population. Data analysis was done with the use simple percentage, mean, standard deviation, tables, charts, and the Pearson product moment correlation with the aid of SPSS version 2.0

Results

Table 1 below captured the measurement of the effect of the use of AI tools on healthcare workers' productivity and efficiency the 5-Point Likert scale measurement was used to determine the extent to which AI impact on workers' productivity and efficiency. To this effect, the result as shown in table 6 below indicated that there was a strong positive response ($\bar{x}=4.4/SD=2.2$) for AI tools helping in reducing time spent on administrative tasks. Again, the result revealed a strong positive response ($\bar{x}=4.3/SD=2.2$) for AI tools enhancing ones ability

to accomplish complex tasks and still producing the desired. Also, the result indicated a strong mean response ($\bar{x} < 4.1 / SD = 2.05$) for AI tools helping to improve accuracy and reduce error in diagnostic and treatments. Similarly, the result reveal there was a strong positive response ($\bar{x} < 4.1 / SD = 2.05$) for AI tools helping to streamline workflow. Lastly, the result indicated a strong positive mean response ($\bar{x} < 4.2 / SD = 2.1$) for AI tool generally enhancing transformative impacts on workers’ productivity and efficiency. Statistically, since all the variables measuring the effects of AI o workers’ productivity and efficiency had a positive response it was accepted that there is a significant relationship between the use of AI tools and workers’ productivity and efficiency based on the overall calculated stronger mean responses (value) which was equal to/higher than the criterion mean value ($\bar{x} > 3.00$ or $\bar{x} = 3.00$)

Table 1: Results of the Effect of AI on Healthcare Workers’ Productivity and Efficiency

S/N	Measurable Variables	Observed Responses					Mean (X)	Standard Deviation (SD)	Research Decision
		SA	A	U	D	SD			
1	AI tools helps in reducing time spent on administrative tasks	249 62.2%	110 27.5%	5 1.3%	30 7.5%	6 1.5%	4.4	2.2	Accepted
2	AI tools enhances ones ability to accomplish complex tasks and still producing the desired results	189 7.7%	124 %	9 12.5%	35 48.1 %	3 7%	4.3	2.2	Accepted
3	AI tools helps to improve accuracy and reduce error in diagnostic and treatments.	155 8.2%	159 0%	47 12%	2 40.4 %	37 39.4 %	4.1	2.05	Accepted
4	AI tools help to streamline workflow	191 15.3%	92 0.5%	49 12%	60 48.1 %	8 24%	4.1	2.05	Accepted
5	AI tool generally enhances transformative impacts on workers’ productivity and efficiency.	125 31.3%	179 19.7%	87 21.7%	0 0%	9 2.3	4.2	2.1	Accepted

Source: Fieldwork, (2025)

Table 2: Critically, the last measurement of the impact of AI on job displacement among healthcare workers was linked with a description of healthcare workers who had been laid off from their jobs between 1-5 years ago. As such the survey result as indicated in fig 10 below revealed that 1.6% of the population affirmed that the rate of laid-off staff was extremely high,

38.8% of them affirmed that the rate of laid-off staff was high, 44% of the population had no idea if staff had been laid off between 1-5 years ago. Conversely, 11.6% of the population affirmed that the rate of staff that had been laid of between 1-5 years ago was low, while 4% of them affirmed that the rate of healthcare staff laid off between 1-5 Years ago was very low.

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

Hypotheses

Table 2 below further revealed the result of the Pearson’s correlation test showed the two critical values which determine the level of association between integration of AI and productivity/efficiency of healthcare workers. To this effect, it revealed that there is a strong positive the linear by linear association (.743**) between integration of AI and productivity/efficiency of healthcare workers. It further indicated significance of the association between the two variables based on a 2-tailed correlation significance. As such, the Pearson test result (P<0.002) implies that there is a significant relationship between integration of AI and Healthcare workers’ productivity/efficiency. Hence, Since the P value derived from the test is less than the criterion value of P<0.05, the above stated null hypothesis is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis is restated, which confirmed that there is a significant relationship between integration of AI and Healthcare workers’ productivity/efficiency.

Tab 2 Result of the Correlations between AI and Productivity/Efficiency of Healthcare workers			
		Integration of AI	Productivity/ Efficiency
Integration of AI	Pearson Correlation	1	.743**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	400	400
Productivity/Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	.743**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	400	400

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Source: Field Work, (2025)

Table 3 showed the result of the Pearson’s correlation test showed the two critical values which determine the level of association between integration of AI and increase in job displacement among healthcare workers shown in table 10 below. To this effect, it revealed that there is a weak negative the linear by linear association (-.356**) between the use of AI and increase in job displacement of healthcare workers. It further indicated significance of the association between the two variables based on a 2-tailed correlation significance. As such, the Pearson test result (P<0.000) implies that there is a significant relationship between the use of AI in healthcare delivery and patients’ satisfaction. Hence, Since the P value derived from the test is less than the criterion value of P<0.05, the above stated null hypothesis is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis is restated, which confirmed that there is a significant relationship between the integration of AI and increase in job displacement among healthcare workers

Table 3: Result of the Correlations between integration of AI and Increase in job displacement			
		Integration of AI	Increased Job displacement
Integration of AI	Pearson Correlation	1	-.356**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	400	400
Increased displacement	Job Pearson Correlation	-.356**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	400	400

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Source: Field Work, (2025)

Discussion of Findings

From the above analysis it has become glaring that the introduction and application of AI in healthcare delivery systems has great impact of healthcare delivery and on healthcare workers at large. As discovered in this current study the need to equip healthcare workers with AI-driven skills is not only good but expedient. This study discovered that more than half of the healthcare worker under this survey had acquired at least one Ai-driven skills to enhance their productivity. Considered to be imperative, the study discovered that the percentage of healthcare worker who are had obtained a skill or training in AI are very confident in applying these skills in their daily routine. These finding corroborate with the findings of Valibour and Indresen (2022) who strongly advocated that health worker who lacks basic knowledge of information and communication technology (ICT) in their regular education, should adopt the certain measures in order to keep pace with the trend of the use of Ai in healthcare service delivery.

With regards to the impact of AI on the healthcare workers’ productivity and efficiency this study discovered that integration and application of AI in healthcare delivery services has drastically added momentum on healthcare workers’ productivity and efficiency. This finding in line with the findings of Andras, Lakshmana, Mohammed, Bhadrappa, Shaifali and Sameen (2024) who postulated that AI improves organizational performance by automating tedious

jobs, enhancing data processing capabilities, and enabling intelligent decision support systems. Also, Iftikhar Ahmad and Siraj-u d-din, (2009) confirmed that training is the only way to develop the organizational intellectual property by building competencies. To increase the employee performance by training and development like the researcher quoted is an important activity to increase the performance of health sector organization.

Much more, this study discovered the concerns of healthcare workers with regards to the probability of job displacement. By the fact, it was evident that the integration of AI in healthcare constituted an absolutely concern for fear of job loss. In fact, it was discovered that some their healthcare workers had lost their job between 1-5 years ago. What is most worrisome is the fear of losing more jobs in the next 5 year to come. Simply put, this study discovered that there is a relationship between introduction of AI in healthcare delivery services and increase in job displacement. This finding is in line with the proposition of Farewell (2024) who submitted that AI's impact on the workforce is multifaceted. It involves the automation of repetitive and routine tasks, changing skill requirements, and job displacement. This can be beneficial for employees as it frees them up to focus on more complex and creative work, but it can also create concerns about job displacement and changes in the demand for certain types of jobs. However, AI is also creating new job opportunities, especially in data analytics, machine learning, and AI development.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Beyond hypothetical theorizing, this study concluded that the integration of AI-based training, tools and skills has a great and positive impact on job (daily routine) of healthcare workers across the Country. This impact however, requires healthcare workers to acquire more Ai-driven skills to enable them keep pace with the ever changing health challenges of their patients.

Given the need to improve productivity and efficiency in the Nigeria's health sector, it is evident that the adaptability of healthcare worker to the use of AI is not merely a good thing but highly imperative, as it is required of them to get more and more familiar with AI-based training in order to enhance their productivity. As such, job displacement appears to be on the rise as healthcare workers fail to get the requisite trainings on the use of AI in healthcare delivery services at the time this study was conducted. This may present a pathetic reality that would leave so many healthcare professional stranded in the nearest future.

To this end, it is recommended that the Government and all health organization in Nigeria, should design a clear organizational approach for AI integration that aligns with existing system goals and objectives; Improve AI literacy for governance members and staff, including foundational education on AI, applications in health care, design and implementation risks, and relevant regulatory guidance.

REFERENCES

- Andras S., Lakshmana P.M., Mohammed, A.A., Bhadrappa, H. & Sameen A.Z. (2024), The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Management Productivity and Efficiency. *Business, Management, Economics and Engineering Journal*. Volume 22 Issue 1, ISSN 2669- 2481
- Dussault, G. and Dubois, C.A. (2003) Human resources for health policies: a critical component in health policies. *Human Resources for Health*, 1.
- Esan T., (2023) The Transformative Impact of AI on Medical and Healthcare Job . Available @ <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/transformative-impact-ai-medical-healthcare-job-roles->
- Farrell, D. et al. (2020). The NHS Digital Academy – learning from the past to look ahead. *Future Heal. J* , Vol 7, 185–188. Royal College of Physicians
- Franco, L. M., Bennett, S., Kanfer, R. and Stubblebine, P. (2006) Determinants and consequences of health worker motivation in hospitals in Jordan and Georgia. *Social Science & Medicine*, 58, 343–355.
- Homedes N., & Ugalde A., (2005) Human Resources: the Cinderella of health-sector reform in Latin America. *Human Resources for Health* 3-1
- Iftikhar A. & Siraj-u D., (2009) Evaluating Training and Development *Gomal Journal of Medical Sciences* July-December 2009, Vol. 7, No. 2
- Kolehmainen-Aitken, R.-L. (2004) Decentralization's impact on the health workforce: perspectives of managers, workers and national leaders. *Human Resources for Health*, 2.
- Mohammed, Y.S., (2024) Applications of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in healthcare: A Review
- Reddy S.J (2024) The Impact of AI on the Healthcare Workforce: Balancing Opportunities and Challenges. *Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society, Inc. (HIMSS)*. All rights reserved
- Rupa B. (2023) Healthcare Industry Jobs: Opportunities and Challenges From a Student's Perspective *IJRDO - Journal of Social Science and Hmanities Research* ISSN: 2456-2971 Volume-9 | Issue-7
- Schmelzer, R. (2019). “Should We Be Afraid of AI?”. *Forbes* <https://www.forbes.com/sites/cognitiveworld/2019/10/31/should-we-be-afraid-of-ai/?sh=6259024331df>.
- Samuels, A. (2020, August 6). “Millions of Americans Have Lost Jobs in the Pandemic—And Robots and AI Are Replacing Them Faster Than Ever.” *Time*. <https://time.com/5876604/machines-jobs-coronavirus/>.

Ukeh B.O., & Anih A.A., (2024) Awareness of Artificial Intelligence Assisted Tools for Research Writing Among Students in Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13826393>

Valibor & Indrasen (2023) The Role of Artificial Intelligence in Increasing the Digital Literacy Of Healthcare Workers And Standardization of Healthcare available at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370265085> DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30715.80165

Wiskow C. (2006). The effects of reforms on the health workforce. Geneva, World Health Organization